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Review Paper

Computational Assessment of Punica Granatum Phytochemicals for Drug-Likeness and Their Prospective Role in Infertility – A Review

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ABSTRACT

Punica granatum (Pomegranates), is currently the subject of contemporary pharmacology because of their exceptional medicinal potential, which is recognized due to their diverse phytochemical profile. Because of their anti-inflammatory and antioxidant qualities, compounds including ellagic acid, gallic acid, ascorbic acid, and thymol effectively improve the reproductive health of both males and females.^{3,4} Major contribution to infertility is mainly the oxidative stress and inflammation; but the compound found in pomegranates mostly acts on supporting hormonal balance, controlling inflammation etc. The computational method has shown usefulness in detecting and analysing phytochemicals that are directing the researcher in various ways in treating infertility or enhancing fertility outcome. A useful method for detecting different bioactive chemicals found in a single medication and exposing their varied functions in treating different medical diseases is this computer study. Ellagic acid and gallic acid aids in protecting the reproductive tissue from oxidative stress, ascorbic acid motivates sperm quality, and thymol contributes anti-inflammatory and anti-microbial properties.^{7,11} Therefore, the phytochemicals from Punica granatum that are helpful in treating the cause of infertility and their function in improving reproductive health are the main highlights of this, but further clinical trials are important to fix efficacy, safety, and dose for human application.

INTRODUCTION

Punica granatum—a fruit that could hold the key to future medicines. *Punica granatum*, or

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pomegranate, is the focus of modern pharmacology because its remarkable therapeutic potential is attributed to its rich profile of phytochemicals, including tannins, triterpenoids, and glycosides.^{1,22} Therefore, for a drug to be viable, it must have drug properties such as solubility, permeability, and bioavailability. These properties ensure that the compound can reach the target site in the body for therapeutic use at an effective concentration. The most widely used guideline for this evaluation is Lipinski's rule of five, which calculates parameters such as molecular weight, hydrogen bond donors and acceptors, and lipophilicity (logP). Compounds that do not follow Lipinski's rule are less likely to be orally active drugs; that is, they should pose zero violation.²⁰ This computational method provides the accuracy to predict the drug-likeness and therapeutic efficacy. Phytochemicals such as ellagic acid, gallic acid, ascorbic acid, thymol, etc., show anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties.^{3,4,5}

Current research focuses on in-silico analysis of not only synthetic drugs but also natural yet ayurvedic traditional formulations as well as single drugs. Hence this article focuses on a single drug, i.e., *Punica granatum*, whose phytochemicals possess the drug-like properties and therapeutic potential. Studies have shown the *Punica granatum* has a strong affinity for the infertility treating targets, indicating that it may be useful for treating infertility. However, this computational technique has its own significance; it should be followed by in vitro and in vivo studies to confirm its effectiveness and applicability. This technique allows for the rapid screening and optimization of potential drug candidates.

Numerous bioactive substances derived from minerals, plants, and Ayurvedic drugs shows relevant action as medicines, but they might need to be optimized to satisfy drug-likeness standards. Rapid virtual screening of these substances,

ADME property prediction, blood-brain barrier permeability, and possible off-target effects are all made possible by computational techniques. Combining this idea with pharmacophore modelling, ADMET profiling, and molecular docking provides a potent method for turning promising compounds into pharmaceuticals that are therapeutically feasible in the age of transdisciplinary research. Early detection of drug similarity helps prevent last-minute experiment failures.

In this review we have focused on phytochemicals that are useful in targeting the infertility-causing target and treating infertility.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Software and servers used for phytochemicals were IMMPAT, the PubChem database for canonical smiles, SwissADME & ChemDraw for downloading the chemical structure, and Molsoft software to determine the drug likeness.

Inclusive and exclusive criteria for phytochemicals:

Inclusive criteria: those which are responsible in treating infertility and also present in *Punica granatum*.

Exclusive criteria: which does not show its role in treating infertility yet present in the *Punica granatum*.

Canonical smiles of selected phytochemicals were taken from the PubChem database.

To get the canonical smiles of each phytochemical, we have to open the database site and then enter the name of each phytochemical in the search bar and press the search option beside it. After that, the compound summary of entered phytochemicals appears on the page; we have to scroll down to the chemical and physical properties row and get the canonical SMILES mentioned under the heading "molecular description." Then copy the canonical

smiles string, and hence repeat this procedure for the rest. (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>)

ChemDraw—to access the chemical structure of selected phytochemicals.

To get the chemical structure of the selected phytochemicals, we have to access the ChemDraw database; in that, we have to click on the structure menu and from there select the option of canonical smiles to the structure option. After that, insert the canonical smiles string and click OK; ChemDraw automatically generates the structure. Table 1 shows the chemical structure of selected phytochemicals.

To find out drug likeness score,

The Molsoft web server (<https://molsoft.com/mprop/>) was used to see the drug-likeness score of phytochemicals. Lipinski's rule of five was used to consider the drug-like properties, which determine the molecules should follow the following parameters: molecular weight of less than 500, C log P less than 0.5, hydrogen bond acceptor less than 10, and less than 5 for the donors. The canonical smiles from PubChem were taken and entered into this Molsoft online software and run to calculate the drug-like properties.

Table no.: 1 Chemical structure of selected phytochemicals.

Sr.no	Phytochemicals	2D	3D
1.	Eugenol		
2.	Thymol		
3.	Limonene		
4.	Beta-caryophyllene		
5.	Gallic acid		

6.	Ascorbic acid		
7.	Ellagic acid		
8.	Quercetin		
9.	Punicalagin		

Table no. 2—Showing the Lipinski's rule and the violations

Chemical constituents of pomegranate phytochemicals	Molecular formula	MW (> 500)	Clog P (> 5)	HBA (>10)	HBD (>5)	No. of violation
Eugenol	C10 H12 O2	164.08	2.21	2	1	0
Thymol	C10 H14 O	150.1	3.43	1	1	0
Limonene	C10 H16	136.13	4.53	0	0	0
Beta-caryophyllene	C15 H24	204.19	5.35	0	0	1
Gallic acid	C7 H6 O5	170.02	0.78	5	4	0
Ascorbic acid	C6 H8 O6	176.03	-1.59	6	4	0
Ellagic acid	C14 H6 O8	302.01	1.53	8	4	0
Quercetin	C15 H10 O7	302.04	1.19	7	5	0
Punicalagin	C48 H28 O30	1084.07	2.83	30	17	3

RESULTS

The drug-likeness is important for drug design, as it tells you the characteristics of a particular drug, specifically in term of bioavailability. In order to determine the medication's bioavailability in the human body, a number of drug similarity metrics

were calculated for a few chosen phytochemicals. This investigation determines whether a phytochemical has the qualities needed for drug development. To assess the drug like properties of the selected phytochemicals, several parameters were considered like Molecular Weight (MW<500 Daltons), Hydrogen Bond Acceptors (HBA≤10),

Hydrogen Bond Donors (HBD ≤ 5), partition coefficient (Log P ≤ 5) and adherence to Lipinski's rule of five (RO5) violations ≤ 1 to observe the bioavailability of oral routes.

The result as presented in the table no 2 indicate that the drug-likeness of selected phytochemicals which exhibits satisfactory levels of acceptable ranges with 0 violations.

DISCUSSION

Data analysis – assess the drug like property of selected phytochemicals

The selected phytochemicals of *Punica granatum* was assess using the physiochemical parameter that influence bioavailability in the human body. The parameters were , Molecular Weight (MW < 500 Daltons) it is important as it involved in the capability of a compound to be absorbed, metabolized and excreted from the body; Hydrogen Bond Acceptors (HBA ≤ 10) influence the solubility and permeability , Hydrogen Bond Donors (HBD ≤ 5) important for drug-receptor interaction, partition coefficient (Log P ≤ 5) gives the hydrophobicity of the drug and ability to pass through the lipid bilayer of the cell membrane and Lipinski's rule of five (RO5) violations ≤ 1 to observe the bioavailability of oral routes. The analysis shows that selected phytochemicals from *Punica granatum* possess the drug-likeness properties based on the evaluated parameters. The results highlight the value of computational techniques in the initial phases of drug development and offer insightful information that can direct experimental research.²⁰

The Lipinski's rule has been so well-established that assess the drug-likeness of a compound based on its physiochemical characteristics. The compound which follows the rule with 0 or 1 violation are more likely to be orally active drugs and more than that are less orally active. The fact that many of the evaluated phytochemicals met the

drug-likeness criteria highlights their potential for further exploration as therapeutic agents.

This scientific review article discusses the therapeutic potential of *Punica granatum* and its phytoconstituents in the treatment of male and female reproductive health. Several compounds have shown promising effects against infertility-related conditions, mainly through their Oxidative Stress, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and cytoprotective mechanisms.^{9,12}

It has been reported that the ellagic acid improves semen parameters against genotoxic insults and thermal stress.³ Punicalagin and related pomegranate ellagitannins have shown effective results in enhancing fertility in preclinical models, which show significant improvement in embryonic and placental development under oxidative stress conditions.^{12,18,19} Clinical evidence shows that pomegranate extract effect sperm motility in sub fertile males. In female reproductive health, flavonoids such as quercetin play a vital role in improving it, as quercetin is linked with improving ovulation, oocyte maturation, embryo quality, and pregnancy rate in women bearing PCOS.⁶ Correspondingly gallic acid has a role in enhancing the sperm quality and attenuating testicular damage in multiple pre-clinical studies.⁷ Other dietetic antioxidants, such as ascorbic acid, have improved sperm motility & morphology.^{4,10} And now the lasting compounds, such as eugenol, thymol, β -caryophyllene, and D-limonene, showed protective roles against toxicant that cause reproductive damage.^{15,16} In particular, eugenol enhanced ovulatory results in PCOS. Thymol improves semen storage quality; β -caryophyllene exerts anti-endometriotic and testis protective effects via CB2/PPAR signalling^{15,16}; D-limonene recovers arsenic-induced testicular damage and improves sperm quality in aging models. D-limonene improved testicular weight and sperm count, improved seminiferous tubule health, and markedly increased testosterone, LH,

and FSH levels in aged rats. Because of its antioxidant qualities, oxidative stress markers decreased, indicating that it has great potential as a natural remedy for age-related reproductive loss.²¹

Hence, the collected findings support the potential of phytochemicals and bioactive compounds present in pomegranates in treating infertility. All

of these work by protecting or improving oxidative stress, hormonal regulation, and cellular protection, thus improving reproductive health for stronger implantation of the embryo in females and also primarily contributing to male reproductive health. However, all the evidence originated from the preclinical models, and well-controlled clinical studies remain limited.

Table no. 3—Summary table of the discussions

Phytochemical	Evidence Summary	Fertility Role
Ellagic acid	Polyphenol antioxidant; safeguards the DNA, enhances the sperm's parameters, and protects embryos in models. ³	Embryo viability and male fertility
Punicalagin, Punicalin, Granatin B (Ellagitannins)	Boost reproductive results; support the placenta and embryo; strong antioxidants ^{12,18,19}	Fertility in both male & female
Isoquercitrin (Quercetin glucoside)	Lower the oxidative stress and increase the rate of ovulation and pregnancy in PCOS ⁶	Ovulation support PCOS & female fertility
Gallic acid	Enhance sperm quality in aging/toxin models. Protects testis ⁷	Male fertility
Ascorbic acid (Vit C)	Increase motility & pregnancy rates. ^{4,10}	Male fertility
Eugenol	Protects spermatogenesis; Restores ovulation in PCOS rats; ⁸	Both
Thymol	Both Antioxidant & improves semen quality in storage; testis protection. ¹¹	Male fertility
β-Caryophyllene	Protects sperm/testis; minimises endometriosis lesions. ^{15,16}	Both
Limonene (D-limonene)	It prevents testicular damage brought on by aging, improved seminiferous tubule health ²¹	Male fertility
Delphinidin	In toxin models Anthocyanin; anti-inflammatory; protects ovarian tissue ¹⁷	Female fertility

CONCLUSION

A complete analysis was done with above phytochemicals that follows the Lipinski's rule of five, suggesting favourable drug-likeness. Although their physiochemical characteristics alighted within the recommended range. The result of *Punica granatum* and its phytoconstituents—including ellagic acid, punicalagin, quercetin, and gallic acid—have been shown to have effective

fertility-enhancing effects. A complex mechanism, especially antioxidant and anti-inflammatory actions, has the potential to improve fertility and reproductive health. Hence, emerging clinical evidence encourages further clinical trials to validate the efficacy and discover cooperative benefits with conventional therapies.

REFERENCES

1. Mo Yaxian, Ma Jiaqi , Gao Wentao , Zhang Lei , Li Jianguai , Li Jingming , Zang Jiachen . Pomegranate Peel as a Source of Bioactive Compounds: A Mini Review on Their Physiological Functions. *Frontiers in Nutrition*. 2022;9(2296-861X).
2. Daina A, Michielin O, Zoete V. SwissADME: a Free Web Tool to Evaluate pharmacokinetics, drug-likeness and Medicinal Chemistry Friendliness of Small Molecules. *Scientific Reports*. 2017 Mar 3;7(1):1–13.
3. Zhu Z, Li W, Ding K, Bastawy EM, Kamel AM, Kou X, et al. Ellagic acid maintains post-thaw goat sperm quality via protecting mitochondrial function from ROS damage. *Cryobiology*. 2025 Jun;119:105231.
4. Rolf C. Antioxidant treatment of patients with asthenozoospermia or moderate oligoasthenozoospermia with high-dose vitamin C and vitamin E: a randomized, placebo-controlled, double-blind study. *Human Reproduction*. 1999 Apr 1;14(4):1028–33.
5. Singh RP, Chidambara Murthy KN, Jayaprakasha GK. Studies on the Antioxidant Activity of Pomegranate (*Punicagranatum*) Peel and Seed Extracts Using in Vitro Models. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 2002 Jan;50(1):81–6.
6. Pourteymour Fard Tabrizi F, Hajizadeh-Sharafabad F, Vaezi M, Jafari-Vayghan H, Alizadeh M, Maleki V. Quercetin and polycystic ovary syndrome, current evidence and future directions: a systematic review. *Journal of Ovarian Research* [Internet]. 2020 Jan 31 [cited 2020 Dec 13];13. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6993490/>
7. Chen W, Qiu J, Hong Z, Yuan J, Wang Q, Zhou W. Protective role of gallic acid in sperm health and environmentally induced male infertility: A narrative review of human-relevant and translational preclinical studies. *Reproductive Biology*. 2025 Aug 13;25(3):101055–5.
8. Sulanaikanahalli Vadyappa Rajini, Halugudde Nagaraja Sarjan, None Shivabasavaiah. Ameliorative action of eugenol on nitrate induced reproductive toxicity in male rats. *Toxicology Reports*. 2024 Jul 30;13:101702–2.
9. Kaltsas A. Oxidative Stress and Male Infertility: The Protective Role of Antioxidants. *Medicina-lithuania*. 2023 Oct 4;59(10):1769–9.
10. Okon U, Utuk I. Ascorbic acid treatment elevates follicle stimulating hormone and testosterone plasma levels and enhances sperm quality in albino Wistar rats. *Nigerian Medical Journal*. 2016;57(1):31
11. Saber TM, Arisha AH, Abo-Elmaaty AMA, Abdelgawad FE, Metwally MMM, Saber T, et al. Thymol alleviates imidacloprid-induced testicular toxicity by modulating oxidative stress and expression of steroidogenesis and apoptosis-related genes in adult male rats. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* [Internet]. 2021 Jun 22;221:112435. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0147651321005479>
12. Sun F, Rao F, Tian H, Li W, Hung H. Potential role of punicalagin against oxidative stress induced testicular damage. *Asian Journal of Andrology* [Internet]. 2016 [cited 2025 Jun 5];18(4):627. Available from: [https://journals.lww.com/ajandrology/fulltext/2016/18040/potential_role_of_punicalagin_ against_oxidative.23.aspx](https://journals.lww.com/ajandrology/fulltext/2016/18040/potential_role_of_punicalagin_against_oxidative.23.aspx)

13. Taghipour Z, Bahmanzadeh M, Rahimi R. The Effects of Clove and Its Constituents on Reproductive System: a Comprehensive Review. *Reproductive Sciences*. 2023 Apr 11;30(9):2591–614.
14. Lucas Fornari Laurindo, Victória Dogani Rodrigues, Minniti G, Cassio A, Tereza Laís Menegucci Zutin, DeLiberto LK, et al. Pomegranate (*Punica granatum* L.) phytochemicals target the components of metabolic syndrome. *The Journal of nutritional biochemistry*. 2024 May 1;109670–0.
15. Anushiya V, Balamurugan S., d Marihrishnaa K. Therapeutic potential of beta-caryophyllene (bcp) in polycystic ovarian syndrome (pcos): insights from rat model studies. *European journal of pharmaceutical and medical research*. 2024 Mar 24;11(4):147–51.
16. Espinosa-Ahedo BA, Madrigal-Bujaidar E, Sánchez-Gutiérrez M, Izquierdo-Vega JA, Morales-González JA, Madrigal-Santillán EO, et al. Potential protective effect of beta-caryophyllene against cadmium chloride-induced damage to the male reproductive system in mouse. *Reproductive Toxicology*. 2022 Mar 19;110:19–30.
17. Park S, Lim W, Song G. Delphinidin induces antiproliferation and apoptosis of endometrial cells by regulating cytosolic calcium levels and mitochondrial membrane potential depolarization. *Journal of Cellular Biochemistry*. 2018 Oct 15;120(4):5072–84.
18. Lin C, Yon JM, Lee BJ, Kang JK, Yun YW, Nam SY. Punicalagin improves chorioallantoic and yolk sac vasculogenesis and teratogenesis of embryos induced by nicotine exposure. *Journal of Functional Foods*. 2015 Sep 14;18:617–30
19. Salem AA, El-Shahawy NA, Shabaan HM, Mostafa Kobeisy. Effect of Punicalagin and Human Chorionic Gonadotropin on Body Weight and Reproductive Traits in Maiden Rabbit does. *Veterinary and Animal Science*. 2020 Aug 22;10:100140–0.
20. Patil AA, Suryawanshi SS. Computer-Assisted Prediction of Drug-Like Properties of Selected Phytochemicals from Terminalia chebula. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Investigation*. 2025 Feb 12;15(2):614–30.
21. SHEREEN M. SAMIR, M.D., M. A. E. H. M., MOHAMED Z. BORAIE, M.D., M. A. M. Effect of D-Limonene on the Age-Related Androgenic Changes in Male Rats. *The Medical Journal of Cairo University*, 2020; 88(March): 599-609. doi: 10.21608/mjcu.2020.104612
22. Noreen, Sana and Hashmi, Bushra and Aja, Patrick Maduabuchi and Atoki, Ayomide Victor. Phytochemicals and pharmacology of pomegranate (*Punica granatum* L.): nutraceutical benefits and industrial applications: a review. *Frontiers in Nutrition* [Internet]. 2025;Volume 12(2296-861X). Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/nutrition/articles/10.3389/fnut.2025.1528897>

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